

TO STUDY THE PROBLEM OF B. ED. STUDENT IN ACQUIRING THE SKILL OF EXAMPLES AND ILLUSTRATIONS DURING MICRO-TEACHING

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Introduction:-

In the B.Ed field microteaching is a very important step for the student teacher for acquiring the teaching skill. In microteaching teacher first conduct the demonstration lesson of the various skill then student teacher prepare a lesson note according to that particular teaching skill. After checking the lesson note by their Teacher Educator he perform that particular skill in front of limited group with the supervision of his co- student teacher and teacher educator.

While conducting that micro teaching lesson student teacher faced various problems. In it examples and Illustration is one of the very important skill in teaching but student teacher faced a lot of problem in acquiring the skill of examples and illustration.

Objectives:

1. To find out the problems in acquiring examples and Illustration skill.
2. To find out the reasons of that problem which acquiring examples and Illustration skill.
3. To suggest remedies on that problems.

Assumption:-

1. Students have the problems in giving accurate examples and Illustrations.
2. Students cannot explain the topic with the help of proper examples and Illustrations.

Hypothesis:-

- If students get proper guidance then they can acquire the skill of example and Illustration.

Methodology:-

For this research researcher selected survey research method.

Population:-

For this present research researcher has selected all the B.Ed colleges in Nanded District as a population.

Sample:-

There are 15 B. Ed. Colleges in Nanded District. Out of these researcher selected one college by purposive sampling method.

Tool:-

For this research researcher collected data by the Questionnaire tool.

Statistical Parameter:-

Researcher used the Percentage for analyze and interpretation of the collected data.

Major Findings:-

- Most of the student's teacher has the knowledge about examples and Illustration skill.
- Most of the students teacher have the knowledge about objectives of examples and Illustration skill.
- Most of the student's teacher gets problems due to lack of content knowledge.
- Students teacher get problem due to lack of fluency in speaking.
- Students acquire the skill of examples and Illustration by observing Demonstration lesson.

Recommendations:-

- Teacher educator should give ideal demo in front of student teacher.
- Teacher educator should give proper motivation to the student teacher.

- Student teacher must prepare the lesson note of the examples and Illustration skill.
- Student teacher must use the proper examples and Illustration in the lesson.

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